

Effect of form and level of N fertilizers on sheath rot (ShR) incidence and yield

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The effect of three forms of N fertilizer at 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha on ShR incidence and yield of IR20 was studied in a pot culture experiment. Ammonium sulfate, ammonium chloride, and urea were applied 50% at transplanting, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. Plants were artificially inoculated with ShR by inserting a single infected rice grain between the leaf sheath enclosing the panicle and the culm of a tiller 65 d after planting. Disease incidence on 5 randomly selected tillers from each hill was recorded 30 d after inoculation.

ShR incidence was significantly lower with ammonium chloride at all the 3 N levels (see figure). At 120 kg N/ha, ammonium chloride recorded the maximum yield (11.5 g/hill) with a disease index of 35.8%. □

Effect of forms and levels of N fertilizers on ShR incidence and yield. TNAU, Coimbatore, India. Mean separation for N rate by DMRT at the 5% level.

Foliar spray to control sheath blight (ShB)

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Fungicides were evaluated singly and in combination under upland and lowland conditions during the 1983 wet season. Varieties used were UPLRi4 for upland and UPLRi5 for lowland. There were eight treatments in upland and seven treatments in lowland with three replications in a randomized complete block design. Plots measured 2 × 3 m in upland and 2 × 2 m in lowland. Plant spacing was 20 cm between rows for upland and 20 × 20 cm between hills for lowland. The first spraying was at early booting (70 d after seeding); the second 2 wk later. Inoculation was with a 3- to 4-wk-old

rice grain-hull culture of *Rhizoctonia solani* inserted between tillers and between plants 2 d after the first spraying. Disease was rated by the Standard evaluation system for rice and severity was computed:

$$\text{Disease severity} = \frac{\text{Sum of disease rating}}{\text{Total ratings} \times \text{max disease rating}} \times 100$$

Under upland conditions, all treatments except PCNB had significantly lower disease ratings than control (Table 1). Under lowland conditions, only iprodione and benomyl gave lower disease ratings (Table 2). PCNB had the highest disease rating and disease severity in both situations. Applying either iprodione or benomyl alone seems to be as good as applying them in combination. □

Table 1. Foliar spray control of ShB on UPLRi5 under upland conditions.^a UPLB, 1986.

Fungicide	Rate (kg/ha)	Disease rating ^b	Disease severity (%)
Iprodione 50% WP	1.5	3.7 a	41.0
Benomyl 50% WP	1.5	3.8 ab	42.2
Benomyl-EMDOC ^c	1.5-1.5	4.4 b	49.6
Benomyl - iprodione	1.5-1.5	4.0 ab	45.1
Triphenyltin acetate 60% WP - triphenyltin hydroxide 50% WP	1.5-1.5	4.7 cd	52.5
Triphenyltin acetate 60% - iprodione	1.5-1.5	4.2 ab	46.6
PCNB	1.5	5.2 de	57.7
Control	-	5.4 e	60.5
CV (%)		6.8	

^a Means of 10 marked plants/treatment with 3 replications. ^b Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by Duncan's multiple range test at the 1% level. ^c Ethyl 3-(3-5 dichlorophenyl)-5-methyl-2-4 deoxo-5-oxazolidine carboxylate (Serinal 50% WP).

Table 2. Foliar spray control of ShB on UPLRW under lowland conditions.^a UPLB, 1986.

Fungicide	Rate (kg/ha)	Disease rating ^b	Disease severity (%)
Iprodione 50% WP	1.5	4.4 abc	49.6
Benomyl 50% WP	1.5	4.0 a	44.4
Benomyl - iprodione	1.5-1.5	5.6 abcde	62.2
Triphenyltin acetate 60% WP - triphenyltin hydroxide 50% WP	1.5-1.5	6.0 bede	67.3
Triphenyltin acetate - iprodione	1.5-1.5	6.2 bode	69.5
PCNB 75% WP	1.5	6.5 cde	72.5
Control	-	8.0 e	84.4
CV (%)		18.4	

^a Mean of 10 random hills/treatment with 3 replications. ^b Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.